

Voltammetric study of copper(I)-thiuram disulphide reaction and its application to the determination of thiuram disulphides

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Abstract : The reaction between thiuram disulphide and copper(I) perchlorate (1 : 1 molar ratio) in acetonitrile has been investigated voltammetrically with a view to arrive at a convincing mechanism of this reaction. The cyclic voltammetric study of this reaction showed the formation of a new product most plausibly copper(III) dithiocarbamate complex. Prompted by the observation that the new complex afforded analytically useful diffusion-controlled peaks at -85 to -120 mV (vs SCE) in differential pulse polarography, a new method has been developed for the microdetermination of thiuram disulphides.

Keywords : Thiuram disulphides, copper(I) perchlorate, cyclic voltammetry, pulse polarography.

Introduction

In continuation of our earlier work¹, the present voltammetric study has been undertaken. Thiuram disulphides, TDs (1) are the oxidation products of dithiocarbamates (dtcs) and form a distant class among themselves. Of the many TDs that are available, only a few especially derived from relatively simple dialkyldithiocarbamates have gained commercial importance as fungicides, antialcoholic drugs and accelerators in rubber vulcanization^{2,3}.

Results and discussion

The CV study of copper(I)-TD reaction in acetonitrile revealed that TDs did not show any current peak either in the forward (negative) or reverse (positive) scan. Copper(I), however, showed a well defined peak at 923 mV in the forward scan and none in the reverse scan, indicating the irreversibility of the electrode process. When TD (in acetonitrile) was incrementally added to copper(I), the 923 mV peak showed gradual decrease in current intensity, two new peaks one at 400–410 mV (in forward scan) and the other at 465–487 mV (in reverse scan) appeared simultaneously and each peak showed corresponding proportional increase in current intensity. This trend continued till copper(I)-TD molar ratio 1 : 1 was reached. At this point, where 923 mV peak completely

disappeared, each of two new peaks attained their full current intensities. The important CV characteristics of copper(I)-TD reaction are given in Table 1. The electrode process is diffusion controlled and is evident from the data showing direct proportionality between peak current I_{pc} or I_{pa} and \sqrt{v} (v = scan rate) (Table 2). It may be mentioned that data pertaining to tetramethylthiuram disulphides has been given in Table 2. The data for other TDs has also been obtained and shows similar behavior/trend.

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for thiuram disulphides in the presence of copper(I) (1 : 1 molar ratio) in acetonitrile

Thiuram disulphide	With copper(I) perchlorate			
	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	E° (mV)
Tetramethyl	410	480	70	445.0
Tetraethyl	408	485	77	446.5
Tetra- <i>n</i> -propyl	402	487	85	444.5
Tetra- <i>n</i> -butyl	400	465	65	432.5
Tetrabenzyl	405	469	64	437.0

Table 2. Effect of scan rate of peak current of tetramethylthiuram disulphide (TMTD) in the presence of copper(I) perchlorate (1 : 1 molar ratio) in acetonitrile

Scan rate, v (mV s ⁻¹)	\sqrt{v}	Cathodic peak		Anodic peak	
		current I_{pc} (μ A)	current $-I_{pa}$ (μ A)		
20	4.5	0.94	0.95		
30	5.5	1.09	1.07		
50	7.1	1.34	1.34		
80	8.9	1.66	1.55		
100	10.0	1.83	1.66		
150	12.3	2.21	1.83		
200	14.1	2.54	1.94		

Table 3. Differential pulse polarographic and calibration parameters for thiuram disulphides in the presence of copper(I) perchlorate (1 : 1 molar ratio) in acetonitrile

Thiuram disulphide	Differential pulse polarographic parameters		Calibration parameters		
	As such E_p (mV) vs SCE	In the presence of copper(I) perchlorate E_p (mV) vs SCE (-ve)	Linearity range ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Slope	Intercept
Tetramethyl	260	120	3.8	0.1918	-0.0005
Tetraethyl	320	90	4.6	0.1729	-0.0003
Tetra- <i>n</i> -propyl	275	85	5.6	0.1380	-0.0009
Tetra- <i>n</i> -butyl	310	95	6.6	0.1584	-0.0006
Tetrabenzyl	340	100	6.8	0.1168	-0.0005

The changes in voltammograms in terms of disappearance of 923 mV peak (due to copper(I)) and appearance of the new peaks (at 400–410 mV and 465–487 mV respectively) clearly indicate that the above reaction proceed through the formation of new product, most plausibly bisdithiocarbamatocopper(III) perchlorate (2), which undergoes reduction in the forward scan (showing peak at 400–410 mV) and oxidation in the reverse

scan (showing peak at 465–487 mV) and in doing so it involves one-electron change. The copper(III) complexes

of the type (2) have been synthesized through the reaction of copper(I) and thiuram disulphides and is quite well known⁴. The observation that solution obtained on mixing copper(I) and TD (each in acetonitrile) is reacted with potassium iodide and liberates iodine indicating that the intermediate contains copper not as copper(I) but in its higher oxidation state. Copper(I) perchlorate in acetonitrile has been found to yield well-defined diffusion controlled reduction peak at -290 mV, TDs gave similar peaks in the range 260–340 mV. When TD (in acetonitrile) was however added to copper(I), it has been observed that

both TD and copper(I) reagent exhibited decrease in the current intensity of their respective peaks and a new diffusion-controlled peak (-85 to -120 mV) appeared simultaneously showing proportional increase in current intensity. This trend continued till copper(I)-TD molar ratio 1 : 1 was achieved. At 1 : 1 molar ratio where peaks due to both copper(I) and TD disappeared completely, the new peaks attained maximum current intensity (Table 3). With support from CV studies and above observations, it can be inferred that it is the copper(III) dithiocarbamate complex (2) which has generated the new analytically useful peaks at -85 to -120 mV and has been made the basis of the differential pulse polarographic method. It may be mentioned that the negative peak potential values obtained in the pulse polarographic study of copper(III) dithiocarbamate complex at DME are the result of the reduction of electrochemically produced copper(II) dithiocarbamate (formed from copper(III) complex) to copper and free dithiocarbamate ligand. The determination has been made on the basis of calibration graphs drawn between concentration of TD (μg) (added to copper(I) reagent) and peak current (μA). Using straight line equation, the slope and intercept values have been determined (Table 3). The listed TDs with sample size 1.0 and 2.5 μg have been determined with maximum RSD of 1.0% (Table 4).

Table 4. Differential pulse polarographic determination of thiuram disulphides

Thiuram disulphide	Values are mean of five determinations with standard deviations (\pm)			
	Mean peak current, i_p (μA)	Amount found ^a (μg)	Mean peak current, i_p (μA)	Amount found ^b (μg)
Tetramethyl	0.662	0.99 \pm 0.009	1.656	2.48 \pm 0.016
Tetraethyl	0.576	0.99 \pm 0.006	1.418	2.47 \pm 0.022
Tetra- <i>n</i> -propyl	0.580	1.01 \pm 0.007	1.440	2.49 \pm 0.011
Tetra- <i>n</i> -butyl	0.485	0.98 \pm 0.008	1.208	2.48 \pm 0.018
Tetrabenzyl	0.298	0.99 \pm 0.007	1.236	2.47 \pm 0.025

^aAmount taken 1.0 μg . ^bAmount taken 2.5 μg .

Experimental

Acetonitrile (Merck) was kept over phosphorus(v) oxide (5 g L^{-1}) and distilled twice. Tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP) (0.01 M in acetonitrile) was prepared by the method as described earlier¹. Tetramethylthiuram disulphide (Fluka) was recrystallized before use. Tetraethyl-, tetra-*n*-propyl-, tetra-*n*-butyl- and tetra-benzylthiuram disulphides were prepared from respective dithiocarbamates. A water solution of dithiocarbamate was mixed with aqueous iodine. The resulting thiuram disulphide was filtered, washed and purified by known method³. A standard solution of tetraacetonitrilocupper(i) perchlorate, 0.01 M in acetonitrile was prepared by the method as described earlier⁵. Triton-X-100 (Merck), 0.002% solution in acetonitrile was used as suppressor. The experimental procedure is similar as described earlier¹.

Cyclic voltammetric procedure :

Aliquots ranging from 0.1 – 2.0 ml of acetonitrile solution (0.01 M) of each TD were taken in electrochemical cells with each cell containing 2.0 ml of copper(i) perchlorate (0.01 M) in acetonitrile and final volume was made to 5 ml with TEAP (0.01 M in acetonitrile). The cyclic voltammograms of each solution was recorded with the following instrumental parameters; initial potential = 1500 mV ; final potential = -200 mV ; scan rate = 100 mV s^{-1} ; current sensitivity = 0.01 mA .

Pulse polarography procedure : Aliquots (0.1 – 2.0 ml) of acetonitrile solution (10^{-3} M) of each TD were taken in polarographic cells containing 5.0 ml of copper(i) perchlorate (0.001 M in acetonitrile) and volume was made to 20 ml with acetonitrile. Each solution was then mixed 20 ml TEAP (0.01 M in acetonitrile), 2 ml , Triton-X-100 (0.002%) and final volume was made to 50 ml with TEAP. The polarograms of each solution was recorded with following instrumental parameters; initial potential = 400 mV ; drop time = 1 s ; pulse amplitude = 50 mV ; sensitivity = $1 \mu\text{A/v}$; X-axis/cm; and Y-axis = 200 mV/cm (on polarocard). The differential pulse polarograms of each solution was recorded in the same manner as described above. Calibration graphs were constructed by plotting peak current (μA) versus concentration of TD (μg) added to copper(i) perchlorate.

References

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